

Effect of Flipped Classroom Teaching on Paragraph Writing Skills of Pakistani English Language Learners

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Abstract: The current study investigated the impact of flipped classroom teaching on Pakistani BS English language learners in public-sector colleges of Lahore, Pakistan. In addition to it, the study also ascertained the perception of the learners regarding flipped classroom teaching. The research used a quantitative experimental design, collecting data through English paragraph writing tasks as pre- and post-tests and a close-ended survey questionnaire. The sample consisted of 98 BS English students from two public-sector colleges located in Lahore, Pakistan. The students were assigned to a flipped classroom group (FCG) and a traditional classroom group (TCG). Pre- and post-tests were taken before and after 6 weeks of treatment to assess the effect of blended learning. The perception of flipped classroom teaching was gleaned from the flipped classroom group (FCG) via questionnaire. The data suggested that the flipped classroom group (FCG) outperformed the traditional classroom group (TCG). Participants perceived the flipped mode of learning as engaging, interesting, and enjoyable. The study had both academic and pedagogical implications. The findings suggest that flipped classroom teaching can be an effective approach for improving students' L2 paragraph writing skills.

Keywords: Paragraph writing, flipped classroom, Pakistani English learners, blended learning

1. Introduction

Pakistan's educational system now includes English language instruction as a required course, with a growing focus on enhancing linguistic proficiency to compete globally (Khalid, 2020). In particular, writing skills are crucial for language learning because they let students to express themselves clearly and logically in their writing (Huang, 2020). Nonetheless, instructors in Pakistan have long found it challenging to teach writing skills to the novices learning English, especially at higher education level (Khan, 2019). Studies have indicated that conventional educational approaches, which mostly concentrate on written assignments and grammatical rules, are insufficient to foster proficient writing abilities (Khan, 2019). Additionally, the absence of creative methods for teaching writing skills has left students unable to communicate their ideas coherently, which might result in poor academic achievement and little professional options (Rezaei, 2020).

Writing skills, especially paragraph writing skills, have not improved with traditional methods of instruction. Consequently, most Pakistani learners of English find it difficult to compose accurate, coherent, and understandable paragraphs. According to Zahid et al. (2023), Pakistani college undergraduates have trouble structuring and making sense of paragraphs in According to Anwar and Ahmed (2016) English. L2 writing was likewise considered a

difficult challenge for Pakistani EFL learners. The main reason for this flaw is because traditional teaching strategies usually place a strong emphasis on written assignments and grammar standards. These conventional strategies have drawn criticism for their inability to foster strong writing abilities (Khan, 2019). The need for innovative approaches to teaching writing skills has increased, and studies have shown that the Flipped Classroom (FC) approach may improve language learning results (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

The FC approach, considered as blended learning, reverses the traditional lecture-homework format, requiring students to complete assignments and activities in class while still interacting with course materials at home. Flipped learning is a modern classroom strategy that combines one-on-one instruction and small group work to increase student productivity. Instructors provide their students lecture notes and PowerPoint presentations to review on their own time or at home. This method has been shown to boost student motivation, engagement, and overall language skills (Huang, 2020). Its effectiveness in teaching paragraph writing skills to English language learners from Pakistan has not been properly studied.

The flipped classroom approach, which involves reversing the traditional lecture-homework format to prioritize active learning and peer interaction, has received a lot of attention in recent years for its potential to improve student engagement and academic performance (Hamdan, McKnight, McKnight, & Arfstrom, 2013). According to studies, both students and instructors have a good opinion of flipped classroom instruction, claiming benefits such as more flexibility, improved knowledge, and enhanced cooperation (Talbert, 2017; Strayer, 2012). Furthermore, research has shown that flipped classrooms can enhance student outcomes, such as higher grades and greater student satisfaction (Enfield, 2013; Love, Hodge, Grandgenett, and Swift, 2014). As educators explore new ways to teaching and learning, it is critical to understand the perceptions and consequences of flipped classroom education. Pakistani undergraduate students struggle with paragraph writing, despite the importance of English language learning. Traditional teaching approaches, particularly grammatical rules and written exercises, have been critiqued for their shortcomings. The absence of creative alternatives, such as the Flipped Classroom (FC) approach, has resulted in low academic achievement and limited employment options. This project aims to address these difficulties, give empirical data on the efficacy of novel techniques, and provide evidence-based instructional strategies to improve paragraph writing abilities for academic and professional success in Pakistan. As a result, the study seeks to assess the impact of the FC teaching strategy on the paragraph writing skills of Pakistani English language learners at the university level. This research aims to explore the possibilities of this unique teaching technique to help create effective teaching techniques and tools for writing skills education in Pakistan.

1.1 Research Questions

The research questions of the study are as follows:

- a) What is the effect of flipped classroom teaching on paragraph writing skills of Pakistani EFL learners studying in public-sector colleges of Lahore?
- b) What is the perception of students about Flipped Classroom Learning method?

1.2 Significance of the Study

The purpose of this study is to improve undergraduate students' English paragraph writing abilities, which is an essential component of both academic and professional success. The results will help English language instructors improve their teaching methods by offering insightful information about the efficacy of cutting-edge pedagogical techniques, such the flipped classroom approach, in teaching writing skills. The study's findings will be supportive to curriculum designers as well since they will emphasize how important it is to include technology-based tactics into language curricula in order to enhance student results. The study's conclusions will also encourage and motivate scholars to delve deeper into the possibilities of cutting-edge methods for teaching and learning languages, eventually advancing the profession.

2. Related Studies

Qadir and Arslan (2019) evaluated the effect of flipped classroom instruction (FCI) on the writing skills of Iraqi EFL students. The study was conducted at Salahaddin University in Iraq to investigate paragraph writing teaching. The study used a mixed-method research design, including pre- and post-writing exams, a questionnaire for both groups, and interviews for the experimental group only. The results indicated that there was a significant difference between the experimental and control groups, with the experimental group's students outperforming the control

groups on writing examinations.

Ekmekci (2017) evaluated the effectiveness of flipped writing classes in a Turkish EFL environment. The study examined writing performance between flipped and face-to-face writing classes. The study employed a mixed-method pre- and post-test experimental design, including a control group. The experimental group had 23 students, whereas the control group had 20. According to this study, there was a statistically significant difference in the writing abilities of the experimental and control groups, and the experimental group's students at Ondokuz Mayıs University in Turkey were positive about the Flipped Writing Class Model.

Sharom and Na (2022) looked at how the flipped classroom method affected Malaysian students' English writing performance as well as how it affected their motivation to write in the language. It also looked at the relationship between students' motivation and English writing performance. The control group and the experimental group in this study were treated to a quasi-experimental technique. Reliable tests and a validated questionnaire were the study's tools. The results demonstrate that flipped classrooms had a favorable impact on the writing motivation and performance of primary school children in English, as seen by the superior writing motivation and performance of the experimental group that participated in flipped classrooms when compared to the control group. Still, it is unclear whether motivation and students' performance in English writing are correlated.

Sastri and Anwar (2019) examined the effects of flipped classrooms on the recount writing skills of second language learners in science classes in senior high schools in Indonesia. The students were novices in the 10th grade. The study methodology employed a quasi-experimental approach. The study's samples were selected using the cluster sampling approach, with 30 students from the X IPA 2 section serving as the control group and 32 students from the X IPA 1 section serving as the experimental group. The recount text exams served as research tools for the researchers. According to the study's findings, the samples' inability to compose recount texts was not much affected by the flipped classroom, mostly due to their lack of incentive to study online content on their own.

Chai and Hamid (2023) examined the effectivity of flipped classroom learning on the narrative writing performance of Form 5 novices at SMK Lake, Malaysia. The samples (n=60) of the study were assigned to experimental group (the flipped classroom) and control group (the non-flipped classroom) for the purpose of treatment. The data were collected in a Pretest-Treatment-Post test design and analyzed through SPSS. The results were in favor of flipped mode of learning. The experimental group outscored the control group. The study had implications for L2 learners and educators.

Zhao and Yand (2023) examined an impact of flipped course on Chinese L2 learners' writing performance and anxiety by using a pre- and post-test non-equivalent group quasi-experimental research design. The researchers selected the sample of 50 Chinese EFL learners from two intact language classes through convenient sampling technique. Subsequent to this, the participants of the study were randomly assigned to these two intact class to a control group (n=24) and an experimental group (n=26). The study utilized two writing tasks and a writing anxiety inventory gather data from the samples of the study. The outcomes of the study indicated that social media-assisted flipped instructions markedly improved the writing performance of learners and decreased their writing anxiety.

Hence, the reviewed literature suggests that there is dire need of an empirical study investigating the impact of flipped classroom teaching on English paragraph writing skills of college-level Pakistani students because the previous researches (e.g. Chai and Hamid 2023; Ekmekci 2017; Qadir and Arslan 2019; Sastri and Anwar 2019; Sharom and Na 2022; Zhao and Yand 2023) have been conducted in diverse settings (like Malaysian, Iraqi, Indonesian, Chinese, and Turkish) and on school and university levels of populations.

2.1 Research Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, following hypotheses were formulated:

H¹: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) in the pre- and post-test on English paragraph writing skills.

H²: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) and Traditional Classroom Group (TCG) in the end of module test on English paragraph writing skills.

H³: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) and Traditional Classroom Group (TCG) in the post-test on English paragraph writing skills.

H⁴: The students of Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) had positive perception of flipped classroom teaching.

For the present investigation the researchers formulated alternative hypotheses over null hypotheses because the

study is experimental in nature and it aims to test the effectiveness of the Flipped classroom teaching approach on Pakistani college-level students' ability to write English paragraphs. In such cases alternative hypothesis is used to determine if the intervention has a measurable effect.

3. Research Methods

The study employed a quantitative experimental survey research design. In the first phase the researchers utilized pre- and post-test research design while in the second phase survey research method was used where a questionnaire based on Likert scale was prepared (under the supervision of two senior English language teachers) for getting information from members of experimental group only in order to glean the perceptions of the participants about flipped classroom teaching. The process of research was believed to be more suitable in this kind of investigation because it gives direct responses from the respondents of the study.

The instruments used for the current study were paragraph writing tasks against pre- and post-tests and a closed-ended survey questionnaire. The participants were given different topics before pre- and post-tests for paragraph writing. Besides paragraphs, questionnaire was also used as a research instrument. The answer choice of questions was close ended. It was consisted of 15 statements. This questionnaire was prepared under the supervision of two senior EFL teachers. Questionnaire is a reliable tool for research because researcher can get the relevant data quickly and more precisely. Moreover, this is time saving activity.

The samples (n = 98) of the study were selected through random sampling technique from two public-sector colleges: Government Graduate Islamia College, Railway Road Lahore and Government Graduate Dyal Singh College, Lahore, Pakistan. The participants were subsequently distributed, via cluster sampling technique, into the flipped classroom group (FCG) and the traditional classroom group (TCG), with an equal number (n = 49) of participants in each group. The former group received paragraph writing input in the flipped classroom, while the latter was taught in the traditional classroom. Pre- and post-tests of both groups were taken before and after 6 weeks' treatment to ascertain the effect of blended learning. After the treatment and post-test, a close ended questionnaire was prepared to collect data. After preparing copies of questionnaires, then they were distributed to the students (n=49) belonging to flipped classroom individually. After distribution of questionnaire some instructions were given to the students to fill out the questionnaire carefully.

As far as the procedure of the research study was concerned, the researchers collected the data in two main phases. In the first phase, the researchers engaged the participants in paragraph writing activities which was considered as pre-test. Three paragraphs written on different topics by the samples of the study were evaluated and graded by an evaluator. Subsequently, the samples were distributed into two groups: flipped classroom group (FCG) and traditional classroom group (TCG). Two instructors, properly guided by the researchers, treated the classes. The flipped class was taught paragraph writing in flipped ambiance while the traditional class was taught paragraph writing via traditional way. After the treatment of six weeks, another paragraph writing activity was conducted in which the participants wrote paragraphs on three different topics which was considered post-test. The post-tests were also evaluated and graded by two evaluators. Immediately after the post-test, the researchers made the students of flipped classroom group (FCG) respond to the close-ended survey questionnaire to glean their perception of flipped mode of classroom. The data collected through pre- and post-tests and close ended survey questionnaire were analyzed descriptively with the assistance of SPSS.

4. Results

H¹: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) in the pre- and post-test on English paragraph writing skills.

The hypothesis was investigated using the mean pre- and posttest scores of the (FCG) for each session. The mean scores were compared and examined with a paired t-test. All statistical tests were judged significant at a level of $P \leq 0.05$.

Table 1: Pre- and posttest scores' Comparison of flipped classroom group (FCG)

Topics of Flipped Class	Mean Score \pm Standard Deviation		
	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3

Pre-test	9.65±1.58	9.71±1.85	9.61±1.79
Post-test	12.63±1.48**	12.88±1.74**	13.29±1.41*

Independent *t*-test **P*<0.001, ***P*<0.0001. SD=Standard deviation

Table 1 reflects the mean scores of pre- and posttest of FC group for all topics were compared, and the mean difference in the scores of all the three topics was found to be statistically significant (*P* < 0.001). The statistics reflect that flipped classroom teaching is beneficial for the participants of the group and their performance in paragraph writing improved. Consequently, the hypothesis that “There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) in the pre- and post-test on English paragraph writing skills” was accepted.

H²: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) and Traditional Classroom Group (TCG) in the end of module test on English paragraph writing skills.

In order to test this hypothesis, the scores obtained by the flipped class batch and traditional class batch, in the end of module test, were compared using independent *t*-test. *P* ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all statistical tests.

Table 2: Comparison of mean scores of the end of module test among flipped class and traditional class teaching group (n=98)

Groups	Flipped classroom group (n=49)	Traditional classroom group (n=49)
Mean scores (End of Module Test)	15.53±3.76*	9.61±3.90

Independent *t*-test **P*<0.0001. FCG=Flipped classroom group TCG=Traditional classroom group

According to table 2 the mean scores of the end of module test of FC batch and conventional batch were 15.53 ± 3.76 and 9.61 ± 3.90, respectively. The performance of both the groups were compared, and the difference was statistically significant (*P* < 0.0001). This shows that flipped mode of learning proved fruitful. Hence, the hypothesis that “There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) and Traditional Classroom Group (TCG) in the end of module test on English paragraph writing skills” was accepted.

H³: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) and Traditional Classroom Group (TCG) in the post-test on English paragraph writing skills.

For testing the hypothesis, the mean scores of FCG and TCG against post-tests on writing three English paragraphs of different topics were compared.

Table 3: Comparison of posttest scores of FCG and TCG

Method of teaching-learning activity	Mean Score ± Standard Deviation		
	Posttest scores of Topic 1	Posttest scores of Topic 2	Posttest scores of Topic 3
TCG	10.20±1.77	10.04±1.76	10.22±1.75
FCG	12.63±1.48**	12.88±1.74**	13.29±1.41**

Independent *t*-test. ***P*<0.0001. TCG=Traditional classroom group, FCG=Flipped classroom group, SD=Standard deviation

Table 3 indicates the mean post-test scores of FC and conventional SGT groups were compared, and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). The statistics reflect that flipped classroom teaching has been more effective than that of traditional teaching. So, the hypothesis that "There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) and Traditional Classroom Group (TCG) in the post-test on English paragraph writing skills" was accepted.

H⁴: The students of Flipped Classroom Group (FCG) had positive perception of flipped classroom teaching.

In order to test the hypothesis, the data gleaned against questionnaire from participants of FCG were analyzed. The scores of 5-point Likert scale were calculated and expressed as percentages to indicate agreement or disagreement of students with regard to the statements in the questionnaire.

Table 4: Participation and engagement in class

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	22	44.9	44.9	44.9
	Agree	22	44.9	44.9	89.8
	Neutral	2	4.1	4.1	93.9
	Disagree	3	6.1	6.1	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 represents the statistical results of the class participation and engagement constructs. The majority of the students strongly agreed (44.9%) and agreed (44.9%) that learning through a flipped classroom approach enhanced their participation and engagement in English writing class. However, 6.1% of students disagreed with the idea that a flipped classroom increased their engagement and participation in class, while no student (0%) strongly disagreed with the notion. Few students (4.1%) remained neutral.

Table 5: Enhanced learning through in-class discussions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	27	55.1	55.1	55.1
	Agree	19	38.8	38.8	93.9
	Neutral	2	4.1	4.1	98.0
	Disagree	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 reflects the findings of the construct related to enhanced learning through in-class discussions. Most the students strongly agreed (55.1%) and agreed (38.8%) that learning through a flipped classroom approach enhanced their paragraph writing learning through in-class discussions. The number of (4.1%) students remained neutral in responding to this construct. However, 2.0% of students disagreed with the idea that a flipped classroom increased their paragraph writing learning through in-class discussions, while no student (0%) strongly disagreed with the notion.

Table 6: Improved understanding of concepts through flipped activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	31	63.3	63.3	63.3
	Agree	15	30.6	30.6	93.9
	Neutral	2	4.1	4.1	98.0
	Disagree	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 mirrors the findings of the construct related to the improvement in understanding of concepts through flipped classroom. Most the students strongly agreed (63.3%) and agreed (30.6%) that learning through a flipped classroom approach improved their understanding of concepts. The number of (4.1%) students remained neutral in responding to this construct. However, 2.0% of students disagreed with the idea that a flipped classroom improved

their understanding, while no student (0%) strongly disagreed with the notion.

Table 7: Time allocation for activities was sufficient

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	26	53.1	53.1	53.1
	Agree	17	34.7	34.7	87.8
	Neutral	4	8.2	8.2	95.9
	Disagree	2	4.1	4.1	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 reflects the outcomes of the construct pertinent to time allocation in flipped classroom. Majority of the students strongly agreed (53.1%) and agreed (34.7%) that learning through a flipped classroom approach improved their understanding of concepts. The number of (8.2%) students remained neutral in responding to this construct. However, 4.1% of students disagreed with the idea that a flipped classroom improved their understanding, while no student (0%) strongly disagreed with the notion.

Table 8: Enjoyed learning

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	31	63.3	63.3	63.3
	Agree	15	30.6	30.6	93.9
	Neutral	3	6.1	6.1	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 8 reflects the outcomes of the construct pertinent to the enjoyment learning through flipped classroom. Majority of the students strongly agreed (63.3%) and agreed (30.6%) that learning through a flipped classroom approach was enjoyable. The number of (6.1%) students remained neutral in responding to this construct. However, no student (0%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the notion.

Table 9: Engaging and interesting method

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	40	81.6	81.6	81.6
	Agree	8	16.3	16.3	98.0
	Neutral	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 9 reflects the results of the construct related to the engagement and interest. Majority of the students strongly agreed (81.6%) and agreed (16.3%) that learning through a flipped classroom approach was enjoyable. The number of (2.0%) students remained neutral in responding to this construct. However, no student (0%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the idea.

Table 10: Instructor engaged us

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	35	71.4	71.4	71.4
	Agree	12	24.5	24.5	95.9
	Neutral	1	2.0	2.0	98.0
	Disagree	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 10 mirrors the findings of the construct related to the engagement. Majority of the students strongly agreed (71.4%) and agreed (24.5%) that the instructor engaged them during the course of the class. The number of (2.0%)

students remained neutral in responding to this construct. However, (2,0%) students disagreed and none (0%) strongly disagreed with the idea.

Table 11: Organization of more such modules

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	37	75.5	75.5	75.5
	Agree	12	24.5	24.5	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 11 represents the findings of the construct related to the organization of more such modules. Majority of the students strongly agreed (75.5%) and agreed (24.5%) that the instructor should arrange more such modules. No student (0%) remained neutral, disagreed, and strongly disagreed with the idea.

Table 11: Perceptions of the students to flipped classroom as a teaching-learning activity (n=49)

Content and structure	Response on Likert scale					Mean rating
	5	4	3	2	1	
Participation and engagement in class	22 (44.9%)	22 (44.9%)	2 (4.1%)	3 (6.1%)	0	4.2857
Enhanced learning through in-class discussion	27 (55.1%)	19 (38.8%)	2 (4.1%)	1 (2.0%)	0	4.4694
Improved understanding of concepts	31 (63.3%)	15 (30.6%)	2 (4.1%)	1 (2.0%)	0	4.5510
Time allocation for activities was sufficient	26 (53.0%)	17 (34.7%)	4 (8.2%)	2 (4.1%)	0	4.3673
Enjoyed learning	31 (63.3%)	15 (30.6%)	3 (6.1%)	0	0	4.5714
Engaging and interesting method	40 (81.7%)	8 (16.3%)	1 (2.0%)	0	0	4.7959
Instructor engaged us	35 (71.4%)	12 (24.6%)	1 (2.0%)	1 (2.0%)	0	4.6531
Organization of more such modules	37 (75.4%)	12 (24.6%)	0	0	0	4.7551

Table 11 shows that students have a highly positive perception of the flipped classroom as a teaching-learning activity. The mean ratings for all items were above 4.0, indicating a strong agreement with the statements. Specifically, the majority of the students (89.8%) found the flipped classroom method more engaging and interesting compared to traditional classes, with a mean rating of 4.2857, (93.9%) students strongly agreed that the flipped classroom session enhanced their learning, with a mean rating of 4.4694, and (93.9%) novices with a mean rating (4.5510) showed agreement tendency towards the idea that flipped classroom teaching enhanced their understanding of different concepts. Most students (75.4%) wanted more such modules to be organized in the future, indicating a high level of satisfaction with the approach, with a mean rating of 4.7551. Students also agreed that the instructor was able to engage them in the flipped classroom activity, with a mean rating of 4.7959. The majority of students (63.3%) found the flipped classroom to be an enjoyable way of learning, with a mean rating of 4.5714. Overall, the results, by accepting the hypothesis, suggest that the flipped classroom approach was highly

effective in engaging students and enhancing their learning experience.

Figure 1: Perception of learners towards flipped classroom teaching approach

Figure 1 presents a graphic representation of the perception of Pakistani L2 novices towards flipped classroom teaching. The majority of the students thought that flipped classroom teaching enhanced their engagement in the class, and they were convinced that the sessions like flipped classroom should be organized for learning English paragraph writing skills. Most of the students also thought that flipped classroom teaching improved their learning skills through in-class discussions and improved their understanding of different complex concepts related to writing skills. Overall, they were satisfied with this mode of delivery.

Table 12: *Reliability Statistics*

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.968	8

Table 12 reflects the value of Cronbach’s Alpha i.e. .968 which is above the acceptable standard range of 0.70 to 0.90. So, the constructed scale is reliable.

4.1 Discussion

The first objective of the study was to investigate the effectiveness of flipped classroom on teaching paragraph writing to Pakistani EFL learner studying in public sector colleges of Lahore. The results of the current study, gleaned through data, revealed that the flipped classroom teaching effectually improved English paragraph writing abilities of the college-level learners. The findings discovered that there is a significant difference between the average scores or means of the participants on the post-test in overall English paragraph writing skills. The current study’s results are consistent with several findings from the studies conducted previously. For instance, regarding

flipped classroom teaching approach, the findings of the past researches were consistent with Chai and Hamid (2023), Ekmekci (2017), Qadir & Arslan (2019), Sastri & Anwar (2019); Sharom & Na (2022), and Zhao & Yand (2023). The flipped classroom teaching impactfully improved the abilities of college-level undergraduates' abilities to write English paragraphs. Therefore, flipped classroom mode of learning and teaching should be made a regular feature of L2 classrooms.

Another objective of the study was to ascertain the perception of the participants of the FCG regarding flipped classroom teaching. For this purpose, the researchers gleaned data from them through a questionnaire. The analyzed data suggested that the participants had positive perception of flipped classroom teaching. According to them, this approach increased their participation and engagement in classroom activities and in-class discussions. It improved their learning and understanding of various concepts related to English paragraph writing. The participants also suggested that more such sessions should be organized. The results of this segment of the study are in agreement with the past research studies (like Enfield, 2013; Hamdan, McKnight, McKnight, & Arfstrom, 2013; Love, Hodge, Grandgenett, & Swift, 2014; Strayer, 2012; Talbert, 2017) which also indicate positive perception of flipped classroom teaching.

The results of the study can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the flipped classroom teaching created a non-threatening environment for the learners. This helped them overcome the fear of making mistakes and allowed them to engage in a low-risk learning environment. Secondly, learning in and outside the class and doing in-class activities generated learners' interest and enabled them to engage more in the learning process. Consequently, learning becomes more meaningful. Thirdly, flipped classroom teaching contributes to the advancement of reading skills in a pleasant learning environment created to bring about a low affective filter. Finally, the teacher is successful because he involves the participants in learning by providing an active learning environment. In such environments, the instructor motivates the learners to take part in classroom activities. Thus, the learners are motivated to work together and interact with each other, even in a low-performing classroom.

5. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of a flipped classroom teaching approach on the paragraph writing development of Pakistani L2 novices and glean their perceptions towards this approach of teaching. In order to meet the objectives of the study, the participants were divided into two groups, i.e., flipped classroom groups and traditional classroom groups. The former group was treated through a flipped mode of learning, while the latter was taught through the traditional method. Pre- and posttests of both groups were conducted before and after the treatment. The difference between the performances of the groups indicated that flipped classroom teaching had been impactful. Immediately after the treatment, the perception of the participants in the flipped classroom group towards the flipped mode of teaching was ascertained through a questionnaire. Most of the L2 learners had a positive perception of this mode of teaching. They considered this method engaging, interesting, and enjoyable. They also thought that this method enhanced their learning and understanding of concepts related to English paragraph writing. They wished that sessions based on this approach should be a regular feature of their academic life.

The outcomes of the investigation have academic and administrative ramifications. The study is equally beneficial for L2 learners and English language instructors. The study is discerning to the students as it makes them aware of the benefits of flipped classroom teaching as well as learning. The study is fruitful for English language teachers as it provides them insights into the effectiveness of innovative pedagogical approaches to teaching, such as the flipped classroom teaching approach, for the purpose of teaching English paragraph writing skills. The findings of the study are highly significant for curriculum planners as it emphasizes the need to integrate flipped modes of learning into language curriculum. The study's conclusions may assist future researchers in replicating the study with larger sample sizes and a diverse population in different settings.

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